

NDAC/LO/109
1988 June 7

24th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

No activity can be reported for the period March to May.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm, Lindegren)

Cleaning-up and re-writing of software for the production phase continues. The program for reducing standard double stars (STDDBL) has been further enhanced and optimized, and is now practically in its final form. The results of a large number of test runs have been reported in NDAC/LO/107 and 108 (C , C).

The specification of input to the Double Star analysis has been revised in agreement with RGO, NDAC/LO/099.2 (C).

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

The proposal for a point comparison of apparent positions etc between FAST and NDAC has been worked out in full detail, but has not yet been circulated.

Working papers:

- C = NDAC/LO/107 (Söderhjelm, 1988 Mar 30):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIa
- C = NDAC/LO/99.2 (Lindegren, 1988 May 2):
Specification of input from RGO to the Lund Double Star analysis (Rev. 2)
- C = NDAC/LO/108 (Söderhjelm, 1988 June 1):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIb